

SINGLE-PHASE TO THREE-PHASE DRIVE SYSTEM USING TWO PARALLEL SINGLE-PHASE RECTIFIERS

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ABSTRACT

Now a days digital image processing is rapid emerging field with fast growing applications in sciences and engineering technologies. Digital image processing has broad spectrum of applications such as remote sensing, medical processing, radar, sonar, robotics, sport field and automated processes [1-2]. Edge detection techniques are employed for the detecting the edges of the primitive picture. Earlier some primitive methods were used for the image processing. H. C. Andrew et.al. gave the method of digital image restoration [3-5], A. K. Jain and et.al put forwarded the partial difference equations and finite differences in image processing [6]. Image process, image models and estimation regarding the edge detection has been flourished during last decade [7-9]. Most modules in practical vision system depend, directly or indirectly, on the performance of an edge detector and digital image processing. The edge detection process tends to simplify the analysis of the image by drastically reducing the amount of data to be processed and at the same time preserving the useful structural information about object boundaries. An edge-detector is employed to detect edges, in particular boundaries of objects in images which is very important in image processing. Since edges are regarded as primitives of pictures. An edge is said to be occur at a point in an image, if some image attributes changes discontinuously. Edge detection techniques are employed by many researchers with the help of different operators.

In the present investigation edge detection process is employed for different operators and threshold values and its images for 128 x 128 image was obtained by trial and error method i.e. comparing the results below and above the threshold by using higher level 'C' language, which is a user friendly. The comparison of the obtained and the original values of the threshold values is also studied with the percentage of errors occurred in the processing present detection.

EDGE - DETECTION OPERATORS

The idea underlining most edge detection techniques is the computation of local derivative operator. The first derivative of an edge modeled in this manner is 0 in all regions of constant gray level, and assumes a constant value during the gray level transition. The second derivative on the other hand is 0 in all locations, except at the onset and termination of the gray level transition.

So it is exigent that the magnitude of the first derivative can be used to detect the presence of the edge, while the sign of the second derivative can be used to determine whether an edge pixel lies on the dark (background) or light (object) side of an edge.

1) GRADIENT OPERATORS :

The gradient of an image $f(x, y)$ at location (x, y) is defined as the two dimensional vector

$$G [F (x , y)] = \{ G_X / G_Y \} = (df / dx) / (df / dy)$$

For edge detection magnitude of this vector is generally referred to simply as the gradient and also denoted by

$$G [f (x , y)] = [G_x^2 + G_y^2]^{1/2}$$

For edge detection, we are interested in the magnitude of this vector, generally referred to simply as the gradient and also denoted by

$$G [f (x , y)] = | G_x | + | G_y |$$

The direction of gradient vector is also an important quantity.

$$\text{i.e. } \alpha (x , y) = \tan^{-1} (G_y / G_x)$$

Angle is measured with respect to x axis, it is a useful tool for linking edge points that have been detected by using the gradient.

2) SOBEL OPERATOR

Consider the window shown below

X1	X2	X3	-1	-2	-1	-1	0	1
X4	X5	X6	0	0	0	-2	0	2
X7	X8	X9	1	2	1	-1	0	1
			(a)			(b)		

(a) and (b) are masks available for Sobel operator. Component of gradient vector in the x and y direction are

$$G_x = (X_7 + 2X_8 + X_9) - (X_1 + 2X_2 + X_3)$$

$$G_y = (X_3 + 2X_6 + X_9) - (X_1 + 2X_4 + X_7)$$

$$G(x, y) = |G_x| + |G_y| \text{ or } G[f(x, y)]$$

$$= [G_x^2 + G_y^2]^{1/2}$$

In any window, we determine the gradient and compare this with a appropriate threshold. The center of the window is detected as edge only if the gradient in the window exceeds the threshold.

$$g(x, y) = | 255 \text{ if } G[f(x, y)] \geq T |$$

$$| 0 \text{ otherwise } |$$

Using the 3 x 3 area in the computation of the gradient has an advantage over 2 x 2 area. Since it tends to make derivative operation less sensitive to noise. Convolving these masks with an image f (x,y) yields the gradient at all points in the image, the result often. The Sobel mask operation is omnidirectional which means that all black-to-white and white-to-black edge transition are highlighted, regardless of their direction in an image. Sobel operation is more immune to image noise than laplacian operation and it provides stronger edge discrimination.

3) ROBERT'S OPERATOR

This operator has 2 x 2 mask

$$\begin{matrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{matrix}$$

$$\begin{matrix} (r_1) & & (r_2) \\ g = & \sqrt{X^2 + X_2} \end{matrix}$$

Since it operates on small neighborhoods, this operator is very sensitive to noise.

4) PREWITT OPERATOR

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 -1 & -1 & -1 & & -1 & 0 & 1 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & & -1 & 0 & 1 \\
 1 & 1 & 1 & & -1 & 0 & 1 \\
 & & (P_1) & & & (P_2) &
 \end{array}$$

$$g = [P_1 + P_2]^{1/2}$$

This operator is more immune to image noise provides stronger directional edge discrimination.

5) FREI AND CHEN OPERATOR

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 -1 & -\sqrt{2} & -1 & & -1 & 0 & 1 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & & -\sqrt{2} & 0 & \sqrt{2} \\
 1 & \sqrt{2} & 1 & & -1 & 0 & 1 \\
 & & (F_1) & & & (F_2) &
 \end{array}$$

$$G = [F_1 + F_2]^{1/2}$$

6) KIRSCH COMPASS MASKS:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 -3 & -3 & 5 & & -3 & 5 & & & 5 & 5 & & & 5 & 5 \\
 -3 & 0 & 5 & & -3 & 0 & 5 & & -3 & & & & 0 & -3 \\
 -3 & -3 & 5 & & -3 & -3 & -3 & & -3 & & & & -3 & -3 \\
 & & (K_0) & & & & (K_1) & & & & & & (K_2) & \\
 5 & 5 & -3 & & 5 & -3 & -3 & & -3 & -3 & -3 & & & \\
 5 & 0 & -3 & & 5 & 0 & -3 & & 5 & 0 & -3 & & & \\
 -3 & -3 & -3 & & 5 & -3 & -3 & & 5 & 5 & -3 & & & \\
 & & (K_3) & & & & (K_4) & & & & & & & (K_5) &
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{cc}
 \begin{array}{ccc} -3 & -3 & -3 \\ -3 & 0 & -3 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 \end{array} &
 \begin{array}{ccc} -3 & -3 & -3 \\ -3 & 0 & 5 \\ -3 & 5 & 5 \end{array} \\
 (K_6) & (K_7)
 \end{array}$$

7) SHIFT AND DIFFERENCE OPERATORS :

The three common shift and difference masks are

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 \begin{array}{ccc} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} &
 \begin{array}{ccc} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} &
 \begin{array}{ccc} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \\
 \text{(Vertical)} & \text{(Horizontal)} & \text{(Diagonal)}
 \end{array}$$

The shift and difference operators extract the vertical, horizontal and diagonal edges in an image. Each pixel is subtracted from its adjacent neighboring pixel in the chosen direction. The resulting image appears as a directional outline of the object in the original image. This operation is directional, which means that black to white edge transmission are highlighted only in a single direction of travel across the image. The shift and difference operation is the most computationally efficient of all edge enhancement operations, but it tends to accentuate noise in an image.

The shift and difference operation can produce results that are less than 0. This underflow condition occurs when a bright pixel is subtracted from a dark pixel. In these underflow cases, the resulting value is forced to 0. The net effect is that edges going from black to white are brightly highlighted. Edges going from white to black are not, because the bright value is subtracted from dark value. So the underflow condition yields a black result.

8) ISOTROPIC OPERATOR

$$\begin{array}{cc}
 \begin{array}{ccc} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -\sqrt{2} & 0 & \sqrt{2} \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{array} &
 \begin{array}{ccc} -1 & \sqrt{2} & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \sqrt{2} & 1 \end{array} \\
 (I_1) & (I_2) \\
 g = [I_1^2 + I_2^2]^{1/2}
 \end{array}$$

This is the gradient operator. It causes thick edges in output images.

9) STOCHASTIC OPERATOR

SNR = 1	SNR = 9
0.97 0 0.97	0.776 0 -0.776
1 0 -1	1 0 -1
0.97 0 -0.97	0.776 0 -0.776

These masks are poor in presence of noise average low pass filter least square fitting technique can yield some reduction of detrimental effects.

10) LAPLACIAN OPERATORS

Laplacian is a second order derivative operator defined as

$$L [f (x , y)] = d^2f / dx^2 + d^2f / dy^2$$

This operation can be implemented by convolving the mask with an image $f(x, y)$. Note that the Laplacian is 0 in constant areas and on the ramp section of an edge, as expected of a second order derivative.

The three common laplacian edge detection mask are

-1 -1 -1	0 -1 0	1 -2 1
-1 8 -1	-1 4 -1	-2 4 -2
-1 -1 -1	0 -1 0	1 -2 1
(Mask 1)	(Mask 2)	(mask 3)

The Laplacian edge detection operation extracts all the edges in an image regardless of direction. The resulting image appears as an omidirectional outline of the objection the original image. Constant brightness regions become black, white changing brightness regions become highlighted.

ALGORITHMS AND SOFTWARE

In the present investigation development of algorithms for operation of edge detection mask on 128×128 image is done. Applying edge detection mask of size 3×3 and gradient magnitude is calculated at each pixel, which is stored in two dimensional array. The gradient magnitude at each pixel is compared with appropriate threshold and the pixel having magnitude greater than threshold is highlighted and other pixels are made off in order to get the edge detected.

PIXEL GROUP PROCESSING

The edge detection masks considered here is implemented through a process called convolution, which is used to calculate what is going on with the pixel brightness around the pixel being processed. It is a mathematical method used in signal processing and analysis.

Each output pixels brightness is dependent on a group of input pixels surrounding the pixel being processed. Weighted average of input pixel and its immediate neighbours are used to calculate the output pixel brightness value called mask and the array of 3×3 mask convolution coefficient is given below.

a	b	c
d	e	f
g	h	I

Every pixels in the input image is evaluated with its eight neighbours using this mask to produce an output pixel value which is shown in Fig. 1.

a	b	C
d	e	F
g	h	I

Fig.1 Convolution mask

Fig. 1 The spatial convolution process for the Pixel at location I (x , y) creating output Pixel at O (x , y)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & aI(x-1, y-1) + bI(x, y-1) \\
 & + cI(x+1, y-1) + dI(x-1, y) \\
 & + eI(x, y) + fI(x+1, y) + gI(x-1, y+1) \\
 & + hI(x, y+1) + iI(x+1, y+1) \\
 & = \text{Output pixel}
 \end{aligned}$$

The mask is placed over an input pixel and its eight neighbours are multiplied by their respective convolution coefficient and the multiplication's are summed. The result is

placed in the output image at the same centre pixel location. This process occurs pixel by pixel for each pixel in the input image. The equation for the convolution process is

$$\begin{aligned}O(x, y) = & aI(x-1, y-1) + bI(x, y-1) \\ & + cI(x+1, y-1) + dI(x-1, y) \\ & + eI(x, y) + fI(x+1, y) + gI(x, y-1) \\ & + hI(x, y+1) + iI(x+1, y+1)\end{aligned}$$

In the case of a 128×128 line image the edge detection mask operation requires the pixel by pixel process to occur $128 \times 128 = 16384$ times. Each process requires nine multiplications and nine. Additions per input image pixel

ALGORITHM

Steps required in edge detection mask operation of 128×128 image are-

1. Open the image binary coded data file.
2. Read the data from the image file and store it into a two dimensional array for processing.
3. Display the original image on screen.
4. Operate the mask on the input image as stated in previous article pixel group processing operation and calculate value at each pixel.
5. Store value of each pixels in output two dimensional array
6. Display the image pixels stored in output array by appropriate threshold value of get edge detected image

SOFTWARE PACKAGE

Edge detection software is developed in friendly package through C language. In this menu operated package, original image, histogram of the image and results of different edge-detection masks can be seen. Threshold values for the edge detection are noted by trial and error method for different images

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

In the present work, pixel group processing and algorithms for operation of mask on images of different operators are studied and the threshold results are obtained which are shown in the table 1. Table 2 shows the original and obtained threshold values of SOBEL operator. while fig.1 shows the histograms of original and obtained.

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